

Efficient and Budget-Balanced Decentralized Management of Federated Cloud and Edge Providers

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Abstract—Federations of Infrastructure Service Providers (InfSPs) have emerged as an effective practice to cater for demanding applications in cloud- and edge-computing environments, by overcoming the limitations of each such provider (in terms of available resources, geographic coverage etc.). In this paper, we develop innovative mechanisms and policies for the decentralized management of InfSP federations, considering the needs both for resource allocation meeting service composition requirements, and for performing a fair and efficient distribution of profits. Resource allocation is performed by means of a greedy algorithm that includes an opportunistic and an adjustment phase. To determine the payments of participating InfSPs, we introduce an innovative sealed-bid reverse auction that combines VCG and first-price auction mechanisms. This hybrid mechanism, coupled with a sophisticated federation wallet management mechanism, serves as a revenue sink for the federation. Notably, our approach exhibits several nice properties, including efficiency, long-term budget balance, truthfulness and individual rationality. Furthermore, we present how our solution can be implemented in a decentralized, privacy-preserving and trustworthy manner over a blockchain, achieving bid privacy, non-repudiation and public verifiability. Our approach is evaluated by means of extensive experiments, the results of which reveal that resource allocation is either optimal or very close thereto, while individual InfSP profits as well as total federation profits are maximized. The results underscore the inadequacy of relying solely on the VCG mechanism for budget balance, justifying the necessity of our sophisticated hybrid solution.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cloud computing offers ubiquitous and convenient access to virtualized infrastructure and service, allowing for on-demand scalability and flexibility. As cloud computing continues to evolve, we are witnessing a convergence of cloud with next-generation networks, namely 5G and 6G, expected to revolutionize applications in various vertical sectors, such as automotive, media, smart cities, etc. These new era applications offered by Vertical Service Providers (VSPs), require near-real-time data processing, making edge computing an essential element for their realization. Edge computing is a paradigm that brings computation and data storage closer to the location it is needed, reducing latency and increasing efficiency.

Hence, infrastructure and service offerings that combine computational, storage, and network resources from central Cloud Providers, Mobile Network Operators, Edge Cloud Providers, and even Internet of Things (IoT) platforms are necessary to support such demanding applications. We en-

compass all these stakeholders under the "umbrella" term Infrastructure Service Provider (InfSP). Given the coverage limitations of different InfSPs and the diversity of resources and services required to provide complete solutions to VSPs, the formation of federations of InfSPs has emerged as a practice to effectively meet relevant requirements.

In an InfSP federation, different InfSPs come together and collectively create a large-scale virtualized infrastructure to jointly offer services to customer VSPs. Through their participation in such federations, InfSPs can generate additional revenues because they can contribute to the provisioning of solutions that they could not support on their own. The concept of federation is primarily observed in the cloud computing domain but also appears in IoT and network domains. Nevertheless, the formation of federations poses several technical and, most importantly, non-technical challenges.

Federation Challenges. On the technical side, the main challenges are interoperability and operational complexity due to the technological heterogeneity of InfSPs. Several studies (e.g., [1], [2]) and initiatives such as OpenStack, Kubernetes [3], etc., address these challenges. In reality, the primary challenges hindering the creation of large-scale federations of InfSPs are business-oriented and relate to aspects such as economics, trust, privacy, and governance. In particular, in the federation solutions proposed in the related literature [4]–[9] and commercial federations that exist, such as OnApp [10], Google Anthos [11], HPE Cloud28+ [12], etc., InfSPs have to share sensitive information with a central trusted entity (e.g., a Broker) or other InfSPs in the federation (decentralized approaches). This can raise concerns about privacy and security, as well as of validity of information collected from multiple and usually competing entities. Blockchain-based solutions are appealing for the trustworthy management of such federations due to inherent properties such as decentralization, privacy, transparency, verifiability, etc.

Our contribution. In this paper, we model the collective service provisioning in InfSP federations and introduce mechanisms and policies for the (i) trustworthy decentralized allocation of federated resources to VSP service requests and (ii) fair distribution of total federation profits to InfSPs. The resource allocation problem is formulated as a sealed-bid reverse auction, with InfSPs bidding for their resources' usage, aiming to maximize the total federation profit. Recognizing

the NP-hardness of the winner determination process, we introduce a polynomial-time heuristic with two phases: the *opportunistic* and *adjustment* phases. For determining prices paid by VSPs and compensations for InfSPs, we introduce a novel hybrid mechanism incorporating the well-known Vickrey–Clarke–Groves (VCG) [13] and first-price auction [14] mechanisms, alongside a sophisticated blockchain-based federation wallet management mechanism, serving as a sink for the federation revenues. This hybrid approach, coupled with the unique characteristics of our blockchain-based implementation, exhibits properties that neither VCG nor the first price can achieve alone, such as truthfulness, efficiency, fairness, individual rationality, trustworthiness, commitment non-repudiation, public winner verifiability and bid privacy.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: In Section II, we model service provisioning in a decentralized federated platform for InfSPs. In Section III, we introduce our mechanisms and policies for the trustworthy and efficient management of InfSP federations, providing decentralized implementation insights. In Section IV, we present our numerical analysis. In Section V, we overview the relevant literature, and in Section VI, we present our conclusions.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

Resources. Let \mathcal{I} denote the set of InfSPs who form a federation in order to combine their resources for jointly supporting the provisioning of different kind of services, offered by VSPs (Fig. 1). The resources can be of any type, e.g. computational, network, storage, IoT devices, etc., each of them suitable to serve different needs from a service point of view. If \mathcal{R} denotes the set of collective resources, each InfSP $i \in \mathcal{I}$ maintains a set of resources \mathcal{R}_i (where $\mathcal{R} = \{\mathcal{R}_1 \cup \mathcal{R}_2 \cup \dots \cup \mathcal{R}_{|\mathcal{I}|}\}$) that may be located on different geographic regions. Therefore, each resource r is assigned to a certain resource type $t_r \in \mathcal{T}$ and geographic region $\ell_r \in \mathcal{L}$. Given that InfSPs have limited amount for each type of resources in each region, we assume that each InfSP i has a maximum capacity $C(i, t, \ell)$ of resources of type t in geographic region ℓ . For instance, regarding computational resources, this maximum capacity refers to the total CPU power available through VMs or containers. We denote the set of all capacity values in the system as \mathbf{C} .

Service components. A service s is composed of a set of N service components, i.e., $s = \{\sigma\}_N$. A service component σ implements a discrete “function” of a service that is facilitated by a certain type of resource. Thus, multiple resources are combined for supporting a service. Considering the example of a video streaming service, a service component can be a piece of software that performs encoding on the video data. In this case, the encoding service component needs to be deployed at the edge of the network, i.e., in the geographic region of the source that generates the content, and requires a VM/container resource of adequate CPU power for completing the encoding task in the required level of Quality of Service (QoS). Each service component $\sigma \in s$ is enabled by a *single* resource r that satisfies the service component requirements in terms of

Fig. 1. Federation of InfSPs.

the type of resource $t(\sigma) \in \mathcal{T}$ that needs to be assigned and the region where this resource is located $\ell(\sigma) \in \{\mathcal{L} \cup 0\}$. If a service component σ doesn't need to be served by a resource in a specific geographic region, parameter $\ell(\sigma)$ is set to 0.

Service load. Each service generates a load for the underlying resources assigned to it. The load of each service is defined at the level of each service component $\sigma \in s$, i.e. λ_σ . Note that the load λ_σ may be a vector of multiple load attributes. Different load attributes are relevant for each type of service component. Accordingly, the capacity of a resource is characterized by a set of such attributes. In fact, resources and services components that are relevant to each other are characterised by the same set of load/capacity attributes. Such attributes are vCPU power, memory size, volume of data stored, messages send from/to IoT devices, etc. An attribute may be utilized for determining (i) the scaling of a resource allocated to a service component, (ii) the price to be charged for the resource provided or (iii) both. The load λ_σ of a service component σ is exclusively served by a single resource.

Pricing of resources (Bidding). The resources required for composing a service may be contributed by different InfSPs. When registering the resources to the federated platform, InfSPs *announce* a bid $b_r(\lambda_\sigma)$ for each resource r they own, as the *minimum* compensation (in \$/sec) they are willing to receive each time the resource is allocated to any service component σ . The bid is a function of the load λ_σ that the service component generates for the resource.

Service Request Pricing: For each service request s submitted by a VSP to the federated platform, the VSP specifies a price, \hat{p}_s (in \$/sec), that it is willing to pay if the requested service is provisioned. The service is provisioned if the total cost of required resources, i.e., sum of bidding functions $b_r(\lambda_\sigma)$ for involved resources, and an additional charge from the decentralized federation platform, p_m , do not exceed the VSP's willingness-to-pay, \hat{p}_s . The p_m charge supports the operational expenses of the decentralized platform.

A. Real-world Service Example

Next, we elaborate on a real-world service example inspired by the AWS Connected Mobility Solution [15]. As illustrated in Fig. 2, a VSP in the automotive industry (e.g., a car manufacturer) offers a complete connected mobility service that

Fig. 2. Connected automated mobility service example. Service components may be deployed across different geographic regions and InfSPs.

includes on-the-move capabilities such as navigation, location-based services, remote vehicle diagnostics, media streaming, etc., along with functionalities related to the vehicle lifecycle such as predictive analytics, maintenance alerts, etc.

Service components and associated resources. Vehicles are equipped with sensors that collect data related to the vehicle and surroundings. The collected data are delivered from the vehicle devices to the other components of the service through a Radio Access Network that provides coverage across the transport corridors. Therefore, adequate radio resources from multiple antennas located on different regions need to be allocated. In addition, certain service components that are responsible for data collection, streaming, processing, event detection and decision making should be placed in a central cloud as well as in different geographic regions and close to the vehicles, i.e. at the edge of the network, for achieving the necessary QoS. For these tasks, resources related to IoT, data streaming, event detection, data storage, analytics and fleet management, should be utilized.

Service Requests. Multiple automotive VSPs submit service requests to the decentralized federated platform, identifying the geographic regions where they would like to have presence. This request determines the number of edge regions and, consequently, the edge-site service components that should be enabled. The load for each service component in each region should also be specified. For example, if we assume that the IoT component is enabled by the AWS IoT Core resource, then the service component is characterized by four load parameters; namely connectivity, messaging, device registry, and rule engine loads [16]. Finally, the VSP should express its willingness-to-pay at the level of the service as a whole.

Resource bidding. Each InfSP announces a bid $b_r(\lambda_\sigma)$ for each owned resource r that identifies the compensation the InfSP is willing to accept if the resource is allocated to any service component σ . Considering again the example of AWS IoT Core resource [16], the input load for the bidding function is represented by a vector of the four load attributes, that is, $\lambda_\sigma = [\text{connectivity}, \text{messaging}, \text{device_registry}, \text{rule_engine}]$. For instance, the connectivity load is defined as the “minutes of connection”, which accounts for the active connection time of all IoT devices assigned to an IoT Core component. To illustrate, if we assume that 10,000 devices were constantly connected in an one month period, then the total amount of connection minutes would be 432 millions. Assuming

a connectivity charge of 0.08\$ per million minutes of connection, the monthly charge for connectivity alone would be 34.56\$. Note that this price will increase when considering other load parameters. By combining the bidding functions of all resources comprised in a service, we can estimate the total cost for enabling the service.

III. FEDERATION MECHANISMS AND POLICIES

A. Resource Allocation Policy

The federated platform operates assuming service provisioning periods, i.e the resource allocation is updated periodically in fixed time windows or when a significant mass of new service requests has arrived to the platform. The resource allocation for the new-coming services requests \mathbf{S} is determined based on the current resource availability. Given that some resources may be occupied from previous service provisioning periods, only part of each resource may be available. In this study we assume that resources of a service are not reallocated until they are released.

Let \mathbf{X} denote the set of binary decision variables that determine which resources will contribute to each service component σ . In particular, the binary variable $x_{r,\sigma} \in \mathbf{X}$ determines whether resource r contributes to service component σ (for $x_{r,\sigma} = 1$) or not (for $x_{r,\sigma} = 0$). Considering a set of service requests \mathbf{S} along with the respective VSP willingness-to-pay \hat{p}_s for each service $s \in \mathbf{S}$ and the resource bids $\mathbf{b} = \{b_r(\lambda)\}_{r \in \mathcal{R}}$ of the InfSPs, we formulate the resource allocation problem. The objective of this problem is the maximization of the *total federation profit*, i.e., the difference between the revenues that come from the payments (willingness-to-pay) of VSPs and the costs (bids) of InfSPs for the resources utilized to enable the services. The *total revenue* of the federation is given by the following formula:

$$U(\mathbf{X}) = \sum_{s \in \mathbf{S}} \sum_{\sigma \in \mathbf{s}} \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}} \frac{x_{r,\sigma}}{|\mathbf{s}|} \hat{p}_s, \quad (1)$$

which aggregates the willingness to pay for all requests in \mathbf{S} that are eventually served. The value of $\frac{x_{r,\sigma}}{|\mathbf{s}|}$ equals 1 for the services that are provisioned and 0 for those that are not.

The *total cost* of the federation is the cost of all InfSPs for contributing resources to the provisioned services. Considering that the bids $\mathbf{b} = \{b_r(\lambda)\}_{r \in \mathcal{R}}$ of InfSPs for the different resources reflect their cost, the total federation cost is

$$K(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{b}) = \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}} \sum_{s \in \mathbf{S}} \sum_{\sigma \in \mathbf{s}} x_{r,\sigma} b_r(\lambda_\sigma). \quad (2)$$

Note that the bidding functions announced by the InfSPs may not be by-default truthful, i.e. reflect their actual costs. Proper mechanisms should be in place in order to guarantee the truthfulness of InfSPs (see Section III).

The *total federation profit maximization problem* is formulated as follows:

$$\max_{\mathbf{X}} U(\mathbf{X}) - K(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{b}) \quad (3)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \sum_{\sigma \in \mathbf{s}} x_{r,\sigma} \leq 1, \forall r \in \mathcal{R}, \quad \forall \mathbf{s} \in \mathbf{S} \quad (3a)$$

$$\sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}} x_{r,\sigma} \leq 1, \forall \sigma \in \mathbf{s}, \quad \forall \mathbf{s} \in \mathbf{S} \quad (3b)$$

$$\sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}_i} \sum_{\mathbf{s} \in \mathbf{S}} \sum_{\sigma \in \mathbf{s}} x_{r,\sigma} \lambda_{\sigma} z(r, t, \ell) \leq C(i, t, \ell), \quad (3c)$$

$$\forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall \ell \in \mathcal{L}$$

$$\sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}} \sum_{\sigma \in \mathbf{s}} x_{r,\sigma} = \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}} x_{r,\sigma'} |\mathbf{s}|, \quad \forall \sigma' \in \mathbf{s}, \forall \mathbf{s} \in \mathbf{S} \quad (3d)$$

$$x_{r,\sigma} t_r = x_{r,\sigma} t(\sigma), \quad \forall r \in \mathcal{R}, \forall \sigma \in \mathbf{s}, \forall \mathbf{s} \in \mathbf{S} \quad (3e)$$

$$x_{r,\sigma} (\ell_r - \ell(\sigma)) \ell(\sigma) = 0, \quad \forall r \in \mathcal{R}, \forall \sigma \in \mathbf{s}, \forall \mathbf{s} \in \mathbf{S} \quad (3f)$$

$$\sum_{\sigma \in \mathbf{s}} \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}} x_{r,\sigma} b_r(\lambda_{\sigma}) + p_m \leq \hat{p}_{\mathbf{s}}, \quad \forall \mathbf{s} \in \mathbf{S} \quad (3g)$$

Constraints (3a) and (3b) ensure that each resource contributes to at most one service component of each service, and each service component is served by at most one resource of the appropriate type, respectively. For a single InfSP, constraint (3c) ensures that the load generated by service components, enabled by resources of a certain type in a specific geographic region, doesn't exceed the maximum capacity available to the InfSP. Note that the function $z(r, t, \ell)$ is an indicator function that returns 1 if the type and region of resource r equals t and ℓ , respectively; otherwise, it returns 0. Constraint (3d) guarantees that resources will be allocated to either all or none of the service components for each service, not in a subset of them. Constraints (3e) and (3f) ensure that a resource of the appropriate type, located in the appropriate geographic region, will be allocated to each service component. Finally, constraint (3g) ensures that the cost for providing each service does not exceed the willingness-to-pay of the requested VSP.

The combinatorial optimization problem described falls under the category of facility location problems, acknowledged as NP-hard [17]. While optimization tools such as the Gurobi Optimizer [18] can effectively handle small instances, computational time grows exponentially with system scaling. Importantly, these solvers cannot be integrated into decentralized platforms based on blockchain technology due to the absence of support for on-chain solutions in smart contract languages. In this paper, drawing inspiration from the Martello-Toth approximation scheme for Generalized Assignment Problems [19], we propose a polynomial-time greedy algorithm that can be implemented within a smart contract.

Greedy Algorithm. Our greedy algorithm relies on three key notions, namely the cost, value and desirability, as introduced by [19]. In our case, the *cost* for enabling a service component σ is determined by the bidding function of the resource r that

Algorithm 1: Opportunistic phase

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1  $\bar{\mathbf{S}} := \mathbf{S}$  // Currently unserved services
2 while  $\hat{\mathbf{S}} \neq \bar{\mathbf{S}}$  do
3    $\bar{\mathbf{S}} := \hat{\mathbf{S}}$ 
4   winning_value := -1
5   winning_pair := {}
6   foreach  $s \in \hat{\mathbf{S}}$  do
7     foreach  $\sigma \in s$  do
8       foreach  $r \in \mathcal{R}$  do
9         if  $\lambda_{\sigma} \geq C_r$  and  $\hat{p}_{s,\sigma} \leq b_r(\lambda_{\sigma})$  then
10           continue
11         if  $t_{\sigma} \neq t_r$  and  $l_{\sigma} \neq l_r$  and  $l_{\sigma} \neq 0$  then
12           continue
13          $\mathcal{R}_{\sigma}.$ append( $r$ )
14          $d_{r,\sigma} = \frac{p_s}{|s|b_r(\lambda_{\sigma})}$ 
15       end
16        $r_{\sigma}^* = \arg \max_{r \in \mathcal{R}_{\sigma}} d_{r,\sigma}$ 
17        $r'_{\sigma} = \arg \max_{r \in \{\mathcal{R}_{\sigma} \setminus r_{\sigma}^*\}} d_{r,\sigma}$ 
18        $MD_{\sigma}(r_{\sigma}^*, r'_{\sigma}) = d_{r_{\sigma}^*, \sigma} - d_{r'_{\sigma}, \sigma}$ 
19       if winning_value  $\leq MD_{\sigma}(r_{\sigma}^*, r'_{\sigma})$  then
20         winning_value :=  $MD_{\sigma}(r_{\sigma}^*, r'_{\sigma})$ 
21         winning_pair :=  $\{r_{\sigma}^*, \sigma\}$ 
22     end
23   end
24   if winning_pair  $\neq \{\}$  then
25     update  $\mathbf{X}, \bar{\mathbf{S}}, \hat{C}_{r_{\sigma}^*}, \hat{p}_{s,\sigma}$ 
26   end

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is associated to the service component, i.e. $c_{r,\sigma} = b_r(\lambda_{\sigma})$. On the other hand, the *value* that the enablement of a service component brings to the federation is associated with the willingness to pay $\hat{p}_{\mathbf{s}}$ that is attached to the requested service s . In particular, the value of service component σ that belongs to service s is given by $v_{\sigma} = \frac{\hat{p}_{\mathbf{s}}}{|s|}$. This means that all service components are equally useful for the provision of the service. Finally, the *desirability* for enabling a service component σ through a resource r expresses the proportion of the *value* that is generated per unit of *cost*, i.e., $d_{r,\sigma} = \frac{v_{\sigma}}{c_{r,\sigma}} = \frac{\hat{p}_{\mathbf{s}}}{|s|b_r(\lambda_{\sigma})}$. Our algorithm consists of the two following phases:

1) *Opportunistic phase*: In this phase, our algorithm iterates until all services are enabled or no further feasible resource allocations exist (step 2). In each iteration, the algorithm explores potential pairs of resources and service components (steps 6–8) and performs the most “desirable” allocation. Initially, for each service component σ , the algorithm assesses the feasibility of all resources concerning capacity, cost, type, and location (steps 9–12). Note that $\hat{p}_{s,\sigma}$ (step 9) represents the proportion of the remaining budget of service request s that can be spent on service component σ . This accounts for the fact that part of the initial budget $\hat{p}_{\mathbf{s}}$ for a service s may have been spent in prior iterations. If we denote by $\hat{p}'_{s'}$ the portion of $\hat{p}_{\mathbf{s}}$ reserved to serve a subset s' of service components of service s , then the remaining proportional budget is estimated by $\hat{p}_{s,\sigma} = \frac{\hat{p}_{\mathbf{s}} - \hat{p}'_{s'} - p_m}{|s| - |s'|}$.

The algorithm creates a list with all feasible resources (step 13) for a service component σ and calculates the “desirability” score $d_{r,\sigma}$ for each of them (step 14). Next, the two resources with the highest desirability score are selected (steps 15 – 16). Assuming that r_σ^* and r'_σ denote the two most “desirable” resources, the difference between their desirability scores, i.e., the *marginal desirability*, denoted as $MD_\sigma(r_\sigma^*, r'_\sigma)$ is estimated (step 17). If this calculated marginal desirability is the highest that has been calculated in the iteration, the *winning pair* and score are updated (steps 18 – 20). After evaluating all pairs of service components and resources, the resource allocation of the winning pair is performed and the necessary parameters are updated for the next iteration (steps 21 – 22). Intuitively, the algorithm selects to serve the service component that will potentially suffer the highest desirability loss if not served in the current iteration. Our Opportunistic phase has a complexity of $\mathcal{O}(|\mathbf{S}||s||\mathcal{R}|\log|\mathcal{R}|)$.

2) *Adjustment phase*: This phase, not part of the Martello-Toth algorithm, is introduced to capture the specificities of our problem, stemming from the fact that each service consists of multiple components. During the Opportunistic phase, resource allocation decisions are made without considering the service to which each service component belongs. Consequently, certain resources may be allocated to *incomplete services*, where only a subset of the components is enabled. Since incomplete services cannot be provisioned, related resource allocation decisions need to be reversed. In this phase, unserved services are prioritized based on the number of components left unserved during the Opportunistic phase. Resources allocated to the components of incomplete services are then released. Starting with the unserved service with the smallest number of unserved components, our algorithm aims to completely serve as many services as possible. In each iteration, only the service components of a single service are considered, and the algorithm aims to allocate feasible resources at the lowest *cost*. If, at the end of an iteration, the service remains incomplete, it is marked as infeasible, and resource allocation decisions are reversed. The complexity of the Adjustment phase is $\mathcal{O}(|\mathbf{S}||s||\mathcal{R}|)$.

B. Price Determination and Revenue Sharing Mechanism

Even if the resource allocation problem (3) is optimally solved to maximize the total profit of the federation, the determination of payments from VSPs or compensations for Individual InfSPs is not addressed by the solution. In this section, we introduce a *hybrid* price determination and revenue-sharing policy that combines VCG and first-price auction mechanisms, coupled with a sophisticated federation wallet management policy that oversees the revenues of the federation across multiple provisioning periods. Initially, we apply the VCG mechanism because it maximizes the profit for InfSPs, inheriting the desirable properties of VCG [13], including *efficiency* of outcome, *truthfulness* of InfSPs, and *fairness* in revenue distribution. Conversely, the use of a first-price auction ensures that InfSPs can recover their expenses, while VSPs may benefit by receiving a payment discount in the process.

Below, we describe how the VCG mechanism is applied in our case and how potential budget imbalances and individual InfSP profit losses are mitigated with our federation wallet management policy. Finally, we present the modified first-price auction mechanism as a fallback solution when the revenues in the federation wallet are insufficient for applying VCG.

1) *VCG mechanism*: Under VCG mechanism, for each service s provisioned the customer VSP pays its willingness to pay \hat{p}_s . Consequently, the total revenue $U(\mathbf{X}^*)$ obtained by the federation for the provisioning of all services \mathbf{S} is given by (1). On the other hand, the cost $K_i(\mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{b}_i)$ of InfSP i for the resources \mathcal{R}_i contributed to the federation, under its announced bids $\mathbf{b}_i = \{b_r(\lambda)\}_{r \in \mathcal{R}_i}$ and optimal allocation \mathbf{X}^* , is given by formula (2) when considering only InfSP i .

The earned revenues are distributed to all InfSP following the VCG payments. In particular, the compensation of InfSP i reflects the “*social benefit*” that its presence brings to the federation. Hence, the VCG payment for an InfSP i is determined by the total profit of federation when i participates, without accounting the contribution of i in the total cost, minus the total profit of the federation when i does not participate. If we use \mathbf{X}_{-i}^* to denote the optimal resource allocation policies when InfSP i does not participate in the service provisioning and $U_{-i}(\mathbf{X}_{-i}^*)$ the total generated profits in this case, then VCG payment of InfSP i is given by

$$\mathbf{p}_i(\mathbf{b}) = \left[U(\mathbf{X}^*) - \sum_{j \neq i} K_j(\mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{b}_j) \right] - \left[U_{-i}(\mathbf{X}_{-i}^*) - \sum_{j \neq i} K_j(\mathbf{X}_{-i}^*, \mathbf{b}_j) \right] \quad (4)$$

Non-cooperative bidding game. Given that the compensation of InfSPs depends on the bids announced \mathbf{b} , we assume all InfSPs \mathcal{I} participate in a *non-cooperative game*, where MNOs strategically announce their bids \mathbf{b} , each of them aiming to maximize its own payoff. In particular, each InfSPs i determines its bids by solving the following problem:

$$\arg \max_{\mathbf{b}_i} [\mathbf{p}_i(\mathbf{b}) - K_i(\mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{b}_i)] . \quad (5)$$

That is the difference between the compensation that i receives from the federation and i 's cost under the resource allocation determined by the solution of problem (3).

Theorem 1. (Truthfulness) *If the compensations of InfSPs are determined by VCG payments (4), then the truthful behavior of InfSPs when announcing the bids is a Nash Equilibrium.*

Property 1. (Weak Budget Balance Property) *The total revenues of the federation is sufficient to cover the total compensations of all InfSPs when the net benefit generated by the federation is greater than the aggregate marginal contributions of InfSPs plus the transaction fees of the decentralized platform, i.e., when $U(\mathbf{X}^*) - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} K_i(\mathbf{X}^*) \geq \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} MC_i + P_m(\mathbf{X}^*)$.*

Note that the total transaction fees collected by the federated platform are given by:

$$P_m(\mathbf{X}^*) = \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}} \sum_{s \in \mathbf{S}} \sum_{\sigma \in \mathbf{s}} x_{r,\sigma} p_m. \quad (6)$$

The proofs of Theorem 1 and Property 1 are available as supplementary material¹.

As shown in Section IV, Property 1 holds in a variety of cases, indicating the sufficiency of VCG payments. However, this is not universally true. Qualitatively, this property does not hold in topologies where the majority of geographic regions are dominated by a single monopolistic InfSP. For example, consider an extreme scenario where all VSP services enabled by the federation must traverse a region with only one available InfSP i . Then, the marginal contribution of i to the total profit of the federation is $U(\mathbf{X}^*) - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} K_i(\mathbf{X}^*)$, leading to zero total profit when i is removed. In this example, Property 1 does not hold, even when considering only the marginal contribution of i . While the example illustrates an extreme scenario with all services passing through the monopolistic InfSP, a crucial observation is that in topologies with region monopolies, relying solely on a standalone VCG mechanism may not be sufficient. For this reason, we introduce the following step by which we take care of cases where VCG alone falls short.

2) *Federation wallet management*: In several cases Property 1 will hold and there will be a surplus of money stemming from VSP payments that is not allocated to the InfSPs through the VCG mechanism. To preserve the truthfulness of VCG mechanism, it is imperative that the distribution of this surplus remains independent of the outcome of VCG. According to [20], the truthfulness of the VCG mechanism is maintained when assigning the surplus to a designated *sink* entity that is not involved in the resource allocation decisions. To this end, we introduce the following innovative approach: we designate the decentralized platform as the sink entity responsible for storing and releasing potential surplus using a federation wallet. A federation of InfSPs is implemented as a Decentralized Autonomous Organization (DAO) [21], [22] and the management of the federation wallet is governed by mutually agreed rules among members of DAO. The management of wallet is enabled by instances of Auction Smart Contracts (ASCs), as explained in Section III-C.

In cases where Property 1 is not met, the payments from VSPs fall short of covering the expenses of InfSPs. Our wallet management policy is designed to address this *deficit* by leveraging surplus accumulated in the federation wallet, ensuring **budget balance**. Additionally, the policy must consider that an essential requirement for InfSPs to join the federation is the assurance that their individual profits in each service provisioning period will exceed those from independent operation (**individual rationality**). Therefore, the surplus maintained by the decentralized platform primarily aims to consistently fulfill this condition. If the surplus surpasses a *predefined threshold*, an extra portion may be distributed among federation members (**participation incentive**).

Let ψ denote the balance of money maintained in the federation wallet at any given time. In a provisioning period, the decentralized platform determines resource allocation by

solving problem (3), estimates the VCG payments of InfSPs, denoted as $[\mathbf{p}_1(\mathbf{b}), \mathbf{p}_2(\mathbf{b}), \dots, \mathbf{p}_1(\mathbf{b})]$, and it updates the balance ψ of smart contract based on the surplus/deficit of the current provisioning period. Next, the decentralized platform follows the two steps below for the surplus/deficit management.

STEP I - *Guaranteed profitability*. Let \bar{P}_i represent the profit that InfSP i would attain if it were to operate independently (standalone) in the current provisioning period. In order to incentivize InfSP i to participate in the federation, the compensation provided by the decentralized platform should ensure that InfSP i achieves at least the same level of profit as \bar{P}_i . If the payment determined by the VCG mechanism falls short, the difference should be covered by the surplus maintained in the federation wallet. In the case where the standalone profit $P_i(\mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{b})$ of InfSP i is higher than the one achieved by the VCG payment $\mathbf{p}_i(\mathbf{b})$, the final payment should be adjusted to

$$\mathbf{p}_i^* = \mathbf{p}_i(\mathbf{b}) + \bar{P}_i - P_i(\mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{b}). \quad (7)$$

STEP II - *Conditional surplus release*. Assuming that the federation has established an upper “safety” threshold ψ^t to ensure that sufficient money are stored in the federation wallet for effectively handling potential deficit events, any surplus beyond this threshold should be evenly distributed among the federation members. The even distribution maintains the truthfulness obtained by using VCG and can be consider as a federation participation reward.

In cases where our wallet management policy fails to address budget balance and individual rationality, our solution resorts the first price auction mechanism outlined below. Such cases arise in topologies where the application of VCG always results in a violation of Property 1 and, consequently, in a deficit.

3) *Modified first price auction mechanism*: Under this mechanism, for each service request s the InfSPs will be compensated with the sum of their bids of the resources contributing to this service. Consequently, the total compensations $K(\mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{b})$ of InfSPs is given by (2), while the individual compensations can be calculated by the same formula when considering only the resources owned by the relevant InfSP.

By definition the willingness-to-pay of VSPs is higher than the sum of bids of the resources contributing to the service. Therefore, the total payments from VSPs will be always higher than the total compensations of InfSPs. This means that when applying first price auction the federation will always have a surplus to be stored in the federation wallet. However, in this modified first price auction mechanism we assume that part of the surplus can be given to the VSPs in the form of a discount. Note that the compensation $P_m(\mathbf{X}^*)$ of federated platform should be also taken into account. We use parameter ϵ to determine the ratio based on which the surplus is split between the federation and VSPs, e.g., $\epsilon = 0.7$ means that federation receives 70% of the surplus. The federated platform will store a surplus of

$$C_f(\mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{b}) = \epsilon [U(\mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{b}) - K(\mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{b}) - P_m(\mathbf{X}^*)]. \quad (8)$$

¹https://auebgr-my.sharepoint.com/:b/g/personal/ntarzanos_aueb_gr/Ea9YuM713QVHgczmwZRnnQBywjcFswk9WQN2o1glMDJxg?e=aB7pZx

On the other hand, if S' denotes the number of services that are eventually enabled, each customer VSP gets a price discount

$$d_s(\mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{b}) = \frac{(1 - \epsilon)[U(\mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{b}) - K(\mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{b}) - P_m(\mathbf{X}^*)]}{S'}, \quad (9)$$

which means that the final price for service s is $\hat{p}_s - d_s(\mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{b})$.

Note that the truthfulness introduced by the VCG mechanism is maintained for our hybrid solution since the InfSPs do not have the necessary information (service requests, resource availability, bidding function, etc.) for extracting whether first price auction will be applied in any given iteration.

C. Blockchain Implementation

By implementing our sealed-bid reverse auction for federation management on blockchain, we can achieve several desirable properties, namely trustworthiness without trusted third parties, bid privacy, public verifiability and non-repudiation, as follows. We consider that Ethereum or an Ethereum VM compatible blockchain is employed. Each of the VSPs and InfSPs has an account (i.e., a public-private key pair) in its wallet with a certain address (i.e., the last 20 bytes of the hash of its public key). Each InfSP (resp. VSP) account is associated to a budget balance, but also different balances for the different resources it offers (resp. allocates). Each different resource type is digitally represented by an NFT (i.e., ERC-721) that contains all the different characteristics of the resource, i.e., type, capacity, location, etc. Upon resource allocation, the respective NFT of the resource changes owner. Each such NFT has a special public function that, if called, it checks a timer from the allocation of this resource and upon a certain timeout it transfers ownership back to the InfSP where it belongs. Note that, in blockchain, each stakeholder is pseudonymous, but it can be easily mapped to a specific entity, if its public key is known.

The federated auctioneer is implemented in the blockchain as an Auction Smart Contract (ASC) that owns the federated wallet. Since we employ a sealed-bid reverse auction mechanism for resource allocation, it is imperative that bids remain confidential until winner determination. Furthermore, for non-repudiation reasons, it is necessary for bids (and resource offerings) to be collateralized, by means of assets or funds.

Various approaches have been proposed to implement sealed-bid auctions in a decentralized manner, as explained in Section V. For collateralization of bids and resource offerings, we follow a Zether-like approach [23], where, initially, each InfSP that offers resources creates an account, transfers to that account all allocatable resources and locks its account to the ASC. Each bidder creates a new account and transfers to that account its bid in an encrypted form (using Elgamal encryption) and locks that new account to the ASC, thus achieving full bid confidentiality. After the bidding phase, a bidder can open its bid by also providing it along with a Zero-Knowledge Proof (ZKP) [24] on its encrypted bid, so that its previous commitment to the auction can be verified by the ASC. Therefore, winner determination can be performed and it can be publicly verifiable. The ASC can then simply

transfer the value from the VSPs to the federation wallet and the winner InfSPs, transfer allocated resources of the winner InfSPs to the VSP, and unlock unused willingness to pay of the VSP, the accounts of all losing bids, and any unused resources of the winning InfSPs. Note that an ASC factory (i.e., a special smart contract) for creating multiple ASC instances can be implemented, so that multiple auctions to be able to be executed in parallel without any resource or budget conflict.

IV. NUMERICAL EVALUATION

We develop a Python program that sets up an environment of multiple federated InfSPs maintaining infrastructure across multiple regions and a set of VSPs generating service requests. We consider random topologies and also introduce randomness in assigning resource capacities to each InfSP. In order to introduce asymmetries, we explore both “large” and “small” resource profiles for InfSPs. Our study focuses on the demonstration of (i) the performance of our greedy algorithm against the *optimal* allocation, (ii) the additional monetary benefits of InfSPs by participating in the federation (iii) truthful behavior of InfSPs when it comes to resource bidding and (iv) the robust operation of our hybrid revenue sharing and price determination mechanism across multiple provisioning periods.

A. Simulation Setup

Topology. We investigated topologies of [3, 5, 10, 15] InfSPs dispersed in either [2, 3, 5] geographic locations. In each topology, an InfSP have presence to at least one randomly selected region. Additional regions are added with a probability of 0.35, which is determined in a per region basis.

Resource types and capacities. In our evaluation, we focus on AWS’s connected automated mobility service discussed in Section II-A, specifically focusing on three key resources: IoT, data streaming, and analytics. In each region that an InfSP is present may have a “small” or “large” resource profile. A provider has a “large” profile with 35% probability. “Small” profile resource capacities follow a normal distribution with standard deviation of 0.3, and mean values of [10.000 IoT devices, 200 TBs, 1.000 vCPUs], for IoT, data streaming and analytics resources, respectively. Large profile mean values are [50.000 IoT devices, 1000 TBs, 5.000 vCPUs].

Resource bidding. For resource bidding assignment, we refer to publicly available AWS pricing. The IoT resource bid is based on device connection minutes (0.08\$ per million minutes)². Data streaming depends on ingested data load (0.25\$ per GB)³, and analytics resource bid is driven by the the number of vCPUs utilized by EMR and EC2 instances (0.5\$ per hour per instance)⁴.

Service Requests. We evaluated our mechanisms with low, medium and high demand loads, by generating various service requests bursts. Each burst arrives within a single provisioning period of the decentralized platform, with request numbers

²<https://docs.aws.amazon.com/iot/latest/developerguide/iot-price.html>

³<https://aws.amazon.com/kinesis/data-firehose/pricing/>

⁴<https://aws.amazon.com/emr/pricing/>

Fig. 3. Performance of our Greedy against the optimal resource allocation, in terms of the achieved total benefit (i.e. profit) generated for the federation. The percentages identify the portion of total requests finally served for each different service request load scenario (10 to 200 requests).

Fig. 4. Truthful announcement of costs is the dominant strategy for each InfSP. Higher or lower cost declaration leads to profit losses.

ranging between 5 to 200. Each randomly generated service request requires presence to at least two geographic regions. An additional region is added with 20% probability. The load for each service component is determined by a normal distribution with standard deviation 0.1 and with mean values [1000 IoT devices daily connected, 10 TBs streamed per day, 100 vCPUs per hour/day]. Each requests s comes with the price \hat{p}_s that the respective VSP is willing to pay, which again is determined by a normal distribution with a deviation of 0.1 and mean value of price 600\$/hour, which increases proportionally to the number of additional regions.

Decentralized federated platform. We assume platform fee of 0.01\$ per transaction. The monetary threshold for the federation wallet, triggering surplus distribution to the federation members, is set to 15000\$. We set $\epsilon = 1$, indicating that when the modified first price auction is employed, VSPs receive no discount, and all the surplus is stored to the federation wallet to be distributed in subsequent provisioning periods.

B. Numerical Results

Greedy. Figure 3 illustrates the performance of our greedy algorithm compared to the *optimal* resource allocation determined by the Gurobi Optimizer [18]. Specifically, it displays the total profit generated for federated InfSPs across different topology dimensions: 3, 5, and 10 dispersed in 3, 5, and 10 regions, respectively. Each InfSP may have a presence in multiple regions. The greedy algorithm’s performance is

evaluated against the optimal allocation for various service request loads, ranging from 10 to 200 service requests. The results demonstrate that our greedy algorithm achieves optimal resource allocation when there is sufficient resource availability to meet the incoming demand (i.e., more than $\approx 90\%$ can be served). Given that cloud resource are usually assumed to be “infinite”, this is expected to be the most typical case. However, when it come to the “edge” the resource infinity assumption may not be always realistic. As shown in Fig. 3, even in such cases, our greedy algorithm achieves an allocation really close the optimal one, with the worst case scenario being when only almost half ($\approx 55\%$) of the service demand can be served, resulting in $\approx 1\%$ less profit. Importantly, the efficiency of our greedy algorithm appears unaffected by the size of the topology or the number of requests.

Truthfulness. The adoption of the VCG mechanism ensures that InfSPs declare their actual costs when bidding for resources, and the resulting profit is fairly distributed among them. Figure 4 illustrates the profit of an individual InfSP when truthfully declaring its actual cost compared to scenarios where it unilaterally deviates by declaring a higher or lower cost. The results demonstrate that maximum profit is achieved when truthful information is provided.

VCG weaknesses. The VCG mechanism alone cannot guarantee that in each provisioning period the payments of VSPs will be adequate to cover the payments of InfSPs (*budget imbalance*). Figure 5 shows the total surplus or deficit incurred after applying VCG for 18 topologies (represented with different colors) and for various service loads [5, 10, 20, 30, 50, 70, 100]. Three types of topologies emerge: (i) those where the VSP payments always cover the InfSP payments (surplus), e.g. topology 14, (ii) those that may have surplus or deficit depending on the load, e.g. topology 13, and (iii) those that always have deficit, e.g. topology 6. However, even in the case where a surplus is achieve, it is not guaranteed that the VCG calculated payments result in a profit for each individual InfSP greater or equal to their standalone profit (*lack of individual rationality*). This is depicted in Fig. 6, where, for instance, at load of 50 requests, the standalone profit of an InfSPs surpass its profit when in federation with only VCG applied. Our mechanism addresses these shortcomings.

Fig. 5. Surplus or deficit generated when applying VCG mechanism alone - 18 topologies for 7 different service loads.

Fig. 6. Individual InfSP profit when (i) operating alone, (ii) operating in VCG only federation and (iii) operating in federation that adopts our complete solution. Our mechanisms guarantees individual rationality.

Budget balance and individual rationality assurances. Our mechanisms guarantees that InfSPs participating in a federation only gain additional profit without incurring losses. Figure 6, illustrates how our budget imbalance mitigation mechanism addresses the individual rationality weakness by using surplus from previous provisioning periods, guaranteeing no losses for all InfSPs. However, maintaining sufficient surplus in the federation wallet is crucial for this assurance. In cases of deficit-prone topologies, such as those with perpetual deficits (e.g., topology 6 in Fig. 5), or topologies with more deficits than surpluses, there may be provisioning periods where the federation wallet lacks funds to ensure budget balance and individual rationality. Our hybrid solution resolves these situations by employing the modified first-pricing auction mechanism as a fallback solution. This mechanism compensates InfSPs with their bid (minimum payments) and generates a surplus added to the federation wallet for subsequent provisioning periods.

Robustness. Unlike previous figures illustrating our solution’s operation for a single provisioning period and different service request loads, Fig. 7 showcase the complete solution’s performance over 30 consecutive provisioning periods with a number of randomly generated requests in each period. We evaluate multiple randomly generated topologies (over 50). For simplicity, we assume that provisioned services do not span multiple provisioning periods. The focus is on tracking: (i) the balance of the federation wallet, (ii) whether the VCG or first-price auction mechanisms are employed, and (iii) whether individual rationality for InfSPs is guaranteed in each

provisioning period. The results demonstrate the robustness of our mechanism over multiple provisioning periods, effectively managing the federation wallet to generate additional profits for InfSPs. For demonstration, we present results from two indicative topologies with 5 InfSPs operating in 3 regions.

As shown in Fig. 7, for topology 1 the VCG mechanism is consistently applied across all 30 iterations, indicating that this example belongs to the category of topologies with perpetual surplus. Notably, at 12th provisioning period, the surplus reaches the balance threshold, leading the federation to distribute the additional surplus generated per iteration. On the other extreme, topology 2 exhibits constant deficit. Without our solution, in such extreme cases, only the first price auction mechanism would be viable. However, with our mechanism storing surplus to the federation wallet in each iteration where the first price is applied, it becomes possible to employ the VCG mechanism in several provisioning periods, significantly increasing InfSPs’ profits. The majority of the topologies investigate fall between these two extremes, i.e., they were VCG dominant with the first price mechanism only employed in a few provisioning periods. In terms of individual InfSP profit, the results reveal individual rationality is always satisfied. InfSPs facing limitations in standalone operation, such as geographic coverage constraints, can experience significant benefits. Conversely, InfSPs already enjoying substantial profits in standalone operation can also generate additional significant profits through federation participation.

C. Lessons Learnt

Our greedy algorithm achieves optimal resource allocation when the available federated resources can accommodate up to 90% of submitted service requests. Even in more congested scenarios, the algorithm maintains an allocation close to optimal, with a maximum gap of approximately $\approx 1\%$. Our hybrid mechanism ensures the truthfulness of InfSPs, as the dominant strategy is to reveal their actual cost during resource bidding; deviating from this strategy results in a profit loss. Implementing our complete solution maximizes both the total federation profit and individual profits for each InfSP. The VCG mechanism alone cannot ensure budget balance and individual rationality of InfSPs. Combining VCG with our federation wallet budget imbalance mitigation mechanism and the modified first-price auction mechanism is essential for the robust operation of the federation under any circumstances and across provisioning periods.

V. RELATED WORK

Various early studies [1], [2] introduced the concept of cloud federation, emphasizing architectural, technical, and interoperability aspects. More closely related to our work, several studies delve into economic policies for resource allocation and revenue distribution in cloud federation. In [4], [5] coalitional game theory is applied to form profit-maximizing federation among cooperative cloud providers. The authors of [6]–[9] introduce economic policies for federations in a non-cooperative environment where providers act selfishly. All

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